

THE LEGISLATIVE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN STATES GOVERNING THE TERMINATION OF THE EMPLOYMENT CONTRACT, AND THE PROSPECTS FOR THEIR IMPLEMENTATION IN NATIONAL LEGISLATION

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Annotation: In this research work, the grounds for terminating the employment contract in developed foreign countries, the issues of their application are analyzed in comparison with our national legislation. Based on the results of the analysis, theoretical and practical proposals aimed at improving the labor legislation will be developed.

Keywords: Labor code, employer, employee, employment contract, termination, ordinary termination, extraordinary termination, labor legislation.

INTRODUCTION

In the analysis of the grounds for termination of the employment contract, we aimed to analyze the legislation of foreign states, taking into account several specifics. This process analyzed in the legislation of the states, social, economic, religious and moral categories. For this research work, foreign states were selected from the following units:

According to the foundations of the law system - Roman-German, Anglo-Saxon and Islamic.

According to religious moral values - Islam, Christianity, from the Buddhist perspective.

According to the crisis-economic development, the example of developing and developed countries.

According to the regional location - in the case of the Far East, Middle East, East and Western Europe and African countries.

According to the level of strength of democratic traditions and human rights.

The analysis process shows that the labor legislation of the CIS countries is similar. This situation is not surprising, as the previous labor laws of these states were adopted in the 1970s, and the RSFSR, adopted in 1971, was based on the Code of Labor laws, unified and unified forms and regulations.

Along in terms of structure of current labor code adopted by CIS countries, there are a lot of differences between them. According to I. Kiselev: "The labor code

between the CIS countries has a lot of common properties and at the same time each of them has its own characteristics"¹. In fact, during the analysis, we encounter not only uniformity but also in some directions some of any embroider. Below we look mainly in their differences.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The grounds for termination of the employment in Article 77 of the Russian Federation (RF) The grounds for termination of the employment are given as follows.

- 1) by agreement of the parties (Article 78 of LC);
- 2) at the expiration of the term of the term (Article 79 of LC);
- 3) at the initiative of the employee (Article 80 of LC);
- 4) at the initiative of the employer (Article 78 of LC);
- 5) by transfer, appointment or election of another position;
- 6) as a result of refusing to continue the work as a result of the ownership of the enterprise or its submissible change (Article 75 of LC);
- 7) As a result of technical, organizational and structural changes in the enterprise, the case of the employee continued the work of the employee (Part 4 of Article 74 LC);
- 8) the conclusion of a medical certificate, when the employee refuses the transfer of another job (Parts 3-4 of Article 73 of LC);
- 9) rejection by an employee to move with the employer with the employer for production and other economic reasons;
- 10) in case of non-dependencies (Article 83 of LC);
- 11) if it is not continuing the work of this Code and other federal laws (Article 84 of MC).

By agreement of the parties established by Article 78 of the Labor Code of Russia, the grounds for the termination of the fixed -term employment contract after the expiration of the period established by Article 79, as well as the grounds for termination on the initiative of the employee of Article 80 are almost identical to the grounds for termination on the initiative of the employee of the labor legislation of Uzbekistan. The procedure for their implementation is also practically no different. Therefore, we want to pay special attention to the termination of the employment contract mainly at the initiative of the employer and not at the discretion of the parties.

¹ Киселев И.Я. Сравнительное и международное трудовое право. Учебник для вузов. М.: Дело, 1999. – С. 377-378.

According to Article 81 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation, the employer has the right to terminate the employment contract on his own initiative in the following cases:

- 1) the termination of activities or bankruptcy of the enterprise that is a legal entity upon termination of or termination of the activities of an individual engaged in entrepreneurial activity;
- 2) with a reduction in the staffing number of employees by an enterprise or an entrepreneur who is an individual;
- 3) due to insufficient qualifications of the employee;
- 4) termination of the employment contract with the head of the enterprise, his deputies, chief accountant, and in the absence of a position of chief accountant, an employee acting as the chief accountant in connection with the change of owner;
- 5) a systematic violation by the employee of his labor duties;
- 6) a single gross violation by the employee of his labor duties;
- 7) the commission of actions undermining the confidence of the employer, committing theft at the workplace;
- 8) a person by a person of an educational profession of unethical actions at the workplace;
- 9) if the decision on hiring an administrator or accountant is illegal or damages to the employer;
- 10) the employee submits to the employer fake documents or falses the documents;
- 11) in other cases provided for by collective agreements and agreements, the employer may terminate the employment contract concluded with the employee.

Article 83 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation establishes grounds for terminating an employment contract in cases that do not depend on the will of the parties. They are as follows:

- 1) the call of the employee for military service or sending him to an alternative civil service as a replacement;
- 2) the restoration of an employee who previously performed the same work at work by decision of the State Labor Inspectorate or Court;
- 3) lack of appointment to the position.
- 4) condemnation of an employee on a court decision that has entered into legal force to punishment that impedes the continuation of work;

- 5) recognition of the employee completely incompetent on the basis of a medical opinion issued in the manner prescribed by federal laws or other regulatory legal acts of the Russian Federation;
- 6) the death of an employee or employer who is an individual, as well as the recognition by the court of the deceased or missing employee or employer, who is an individual;
- 7) emergency situations (military operations, losses, natural disasters, large disasters, epidemics and other emergency situations) that impede the continuation of labor relations if these circumstances are confirmed by the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation or other relevant state power of the Russian Federation;
- 8) the application of disqualification or other administrative punishment, excluding the possibility of the employee to fulfill his duties arising from the employment contract;
- 9) the termination of activities on the basis of federal laws or other regulatory legal acts of the Russian Federation, suspension of activities for a period of more than two months or depriving an employee of a special law (license, the right to drive vehicles, the right to carry weapons, other special rights), if this entails The loss of the employee is the possibility of fulfilling his duties arising from the employment contract. if it comes;
- 10) termination of the right to access state secret, if such a permit is necessary for the work performed;
- 11) invalidity (recognition by illegal) of the decision of the State Labor Inspectorate on the restoration of the employee at work or the invalidity of the court decision;
- 12) the restriction on the implementation by the employee of a certain labor activity, excluding the possibility of the employee to fulfill his duties arising from the employment contract in the manner established by this Code or other federal law.

First of all, it should be noted that the termination of the employment contract in connection with the violation of the rules established by the Labor Code of the Russian Federation in relation to employment is not included in the grounds for terminating the employment contract in cases that do not depend on the will of the parties, this circumstance establishes the Labor Code of the Russian Federation as a separate basis .

According to Article 84 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation, an employment contract is terminated if it is concluded in violation of the rules

established by the Code or other federal laws, if the violation of these rules excludes the possibility of continuing work, including:

- 1) if the employment contract is concluded with a violation of the court sentence limiting the person in the lesson of a certain position or lesson to certain activities;
- 2) if the employment contract is concluded on the basis of a medical report providing for the person to fulfill the work that does not correspond to the state of health;
- 3) the absence of a document on the education of an employee, if the federal law or other regulatory legal acts on the task performed by the employee require appropriate specialization;
- 4) other circumstances provided for by federal law.

Also, according to this article, the employment contract is terminated on the above grounds only if it is not possible to transfer the employee from his written consent to another work with the employer. This norm in the Labor Code of the Russian Federation is detailed and, given that it also establishes additional guarantees to the employee, it would be advisable to enter it into the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Let's get acquainted with the labor legislation of Georgia, which is considered the CIS state, but it well reflects the elements of the legislation of Western countries, and these updates practically justify themselves. In the TC of Georgia and the act on labor contracts, the grounds for termination of labor relations are not allocated into certain types, as in European countries (Great Britain, Germany, France, Austria, etc.) the grounds for termination of labor relations are not classified separately².

We have a suspension of an employment contract in Georgia on some grounds that lead to the termination of the employment contract. In particular, Art. 37 of the TC of Georgia provides for the following grounds for suspension of labor relations: workers' strikes; suspension of the labor process (locout) by employers; the use of active and passive suffrage; involvement of investigation bodies, prosecutors, court (all expenses reimburses the state budget); during the call for military service and the performance of other civil duties in any form; During pregnancy, on parental leave (subject to appropriate guarantees).³

Men can also take leaves for child care in accordance with the labor legislation of Georgia; during the period of temporary disability (no more than 30 calendar

² Stephan Hardly, Mark Butler. European Employment Laws: A comparative guide (3rd edition). Great Britain. Ltd by: Short Run Press, 2016. – P. 113-142.

³ Labor Code of Georgia. No. 4113 of December 2010. <https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5>

days and no more than 50 calendar days for 6 months); When the employee is on vocational training or advanced training not exceeding 30 calendar days a year, with the exception of the period of advanced training sent by the enterprise.

Article 28 of the Labor Code of Georgia establishes the following common grounds for termination of the employment contract:

- 1) as a result of termination of work provided for by the employment contract;
- 2) after the expiration of the contract;
- 3) on the initiative of one of the parties;
- 4) by agreement of the parties;
- 5) on the basis of a court decision that has entered into legal force;
- 6) as a result of violation of one of the parties to the terms of the contract, the norms of labor legislation;
- 7) due to prolonged disability (more than 30 calendar days or more than 50 calendar days in 6 months);
- 8) in connection with the death of an employee or employer;
- 9) the termination of the activity or bankruptcy of the enterprise that is a legal entity upon termination of or termination of the activities of an individual engaged in entrepreneurial activity without the formation of a legal entity.

The above grounds are of a general nature, in the “act on labor contracts” the grounds for termination of employment contracts are divided into economic, personal and technical and organizational.

In accordance with Article 39 of the Labor Code of Georgia, upon termination of the employment contract at the initiative of the employee, the employee must notify the employer in writing for 30 days. He notifies the employee a month before the termination of the employment contract at the initiative of the employer and gives the employee the salary for a month upon dismissal. Of course, the provisions of this article are applied only if they are not the result of the unskilled of the employee and other guilty behavior committed by himself in accordance with the above act⁴.

From European countries, the labor legislation of Germany does not recognize the concept of termination of the employment contract by agreement of the parties. The termination of the employment contract always occurs for good reason. The termination of the employment contract occurs in two different

⁴ Terminating the employment contract. Ministry of Social Affairs. Gonsiori 29, 15027 Tallin. 2014.

forms. The first is an emergency end (extraordinary termination for good business). The second-simple ending (Ordinary Termination).⁵

For emergency termination of the employment contract, there must be a good reason. Such reasons include the fact that the employee can seriously violate the employment contract, cause significant material damage to the employer, to become completely unsuitable for work due to health, that the employee's stay at the enterprise may entail dangerous consequences for himself, other employees and the employer. Upon termination of such an employment contract, the notification period does not apply. At the same time, the main reasons will be behavioral and personal (related to employees and related to people).

With a simple termination of the employment contract, the employer must comply with at least four -week notification period established by law. This period of notification increases depending on the length of stay of the employee on this employer. This order is presented in the table below.

No	Employment	Pre-Warning Time
1.	2 years of work experience	1 month
2.	5 years of work experience	2 month
3.	8 years of work experience	3 month
4.	10 years of work experience	4 month
5.	12 years of work experience	5 month
6.	15 years of work experience	6 month
7.	20 years of work experience	7 month

Upon dismissal for economic, organizational (operational) reasons, a 2-month notification period is provided for a six-month initial test period. Labor legislation also enshrines the termination of labor relations in two forms. This is the termination of individual (individual) labor contracts, as well as termination of labor contracts in mass order. With massive cancellation, trade unions and the state are also actively involved in this process.

Another of the advanced countries of Europe, France, in labor legislation, the abolition of labor relations is carried out on two different grounds. The first is personal lands (Personal Grounds), and the second-economic-organizational land (Economic, Technological Grounds). The grounds regarding the personality of the employee include: insufficient qualifications; physical inability to complete the task; committing unethical actions at the workplace; a serious

⁵ J. Kirchner and S. Morgenroth "GERMAN EMPLOYMENT & LABOUR LAW" Handbook. Verband der Auslandsbanken in Deutschland. 3rd Edition 2017. Page 11.

violation of the terms of the contract and the rules of the internal labor schedule; causing harm to the property of the employer and other employees; lack of workplace without a good reason; and so on.⁶

Economic reasons include: economic difficulties; reduction of jobs; technological changes; The liquidation of the enterprise, etc. In France, termination of the employment contract is also sole and public. Upon termination of an individual employment contract, the employer holds a joint meeting with the employee, representative of the employees in case of reason to dismiss the employee. He warns the parties about this in five days. At the meeting, the employer justifies the reasons for the dismissal of the employee and issues a certificate of this, Dali points out. In case of an employee obey within 15 days, he can make a proposal for negotiations.

We believe that such a procedure will reduce disputes and slightly reduce the likelihood of considering cases of restoration in the courts.

Below we will analyze the Egyptian labor legislation, one of the states where Islam has deeply rooted in society, and this is also reflected in legislative norms. First of all, we consider it appropriate to dwell on its specific aspects. In the Islamic model of labor relations, social etiquette at the workplace (code of conduct) and ensuring social justice are the main concepts that need to be followed. The social responsibility of the employer and employees and the infidelity in the remuneration of the enterprise and employees are elements that ensure performance and mutual trust at work. Accordingly, the grounds for dismissal are also more directly related to moral standards.⁷

According to the labor legislation of the Arab Republic of Egypt, the employment contract is terminated immediately (without delay) in the following cases:

- 1) the spread of misinformation or misleading information;
- 2) the intentional committing of technical errors in the process of work, which can cause serious damage to the employer (while the employer is obliged to notify the relevant authority within 24 hours);
- 3) the commission of actions contrary to the rules of the internal labor schedule, which pose a serious danger to other employees (the employee must be familiar with the relevant rules in advance);
- 4) the absence at the workplace during the year without a good reason for 20 days, the continuous absence of more than 10 days (for the first case, the period of notification is used 10 days, and for the second case-5 days);

⁶ Flichy Grange Avocates / Proud Member of L&E Global. Employment Law Overview France 2019-2020. Page 20-21.

⁷ Jawad Syed & Abbas Ali. "Principles of employment relations in Islam: a normative view". 2010. Page 13.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/240258852>

- 6) disclosure of commercial secrets;
- 7) the simultaneous conduct of activities against the employer or competitor at another enterprise;
- 8) reception or exposure to alcoholic products and other psychotropic substances in the workplace;
- 9) causing physical harm to the employer or colleagues;
- 10) committing sexual harassment or other humiliation of female employees⁸.

The grounds for terminating the employment contract using the term of notification are:

- 1) termination of a fixed -term employment contract after the expiration of the term;
- 2) if the contract is concluded with an agreement on a certain work, it cannot be terminated until this work is completed. Cancellation after work is possible;
- 3) on the initiative of the employee and by agreement of the parties;
- 4) insufficient qualifications of an employee for health reasons;
- 5) liquidation of the enterprise, reduction of jobs and other reasons associated with production.

A preliminary notification is not made during the vacation of the employee or during his temporary illness. He will begin to expire when he returns to work. In the above cases, if the employee has worked on this employee for less than 10 years, the notification period should not be less than 2 months. At least 3 months if you have worked for more than 10 years. This period of notification may be extended. The question of reduction is resolved by the body that dealt with labor issues, if necessary, in the interests of the employee.

From the countries of the Far East, labor contracts in Japan vary depending on the size of the companies. Large corporations have long-term employment contracts (Long-Term Employment Relationship). In fact, in the Civil Code of Japan, this is a type of contract that an employee or employer can terminate at any time, observing the two -week period of notification. The parties freely determine the terms of the contract and may establish that the employer is obliged not to dismiss the employee for no good reason, and the employee must serve him faithfully and constantly improve his qualifications⁹. Nevertheless, the Law on Labor Standards of Japan established several procedures regarding dismissal,¹⁰.

⁸ Labor Law and Employment Relations. Business Studies Division, The American University in Cairo. 2003.

⁹ Atsushi Tsuneki and Manabu Matsunaka. LABOR RELATIONS AND LABOR LAW IN JAPAN. Compilation © 2011 Pacific Rim Law & Policy Journal Association. Page 18.

¹⁰ Labor Standards Act (Act No. 49 of April 7, 1947).

According to his article 19, the employer cannot dismiss the employee during the period of incapacity for work and treatment, not exceeding 30 days, as well as during the period of maternity leave. If the company is completely closed as a result of natural disasters or technological changes, the employee is paid the appropriate compensation and the employment contract is terminated with it.

According to Article 20 of the above act, the preliminary notification period is at least 30 calendar days. This period of notification does not apply to: employees engaged in daytime work; employees working under a contract concluded for a period of not more than two months; employees engaged in seasonal work for less than four months; persons undergoing a preliminary test period; persons systematically and once grossly violating the rules of the internal labor schedule.

CONCLUSION

After analyzing the paragraphs from the above chapters, both on the theoretical and on a practical basis, we came to the conclusion that:

Firstly, in the CIS countries, in particular in Uzbekistan, the attitude to labor contracts remained traditional. The application of a modern European psychological approach to labor contracts, based on practical offers that we give in the above paragraph, has become a requirement of time. Because for today's employee, a sense of satisfaction with his work, social relations between the employer and employees, incentives, mutual trust, motivation and other factors are more important than material things.

Secondly, since even in our country, most employees adhere to Islamic dogmas regarding their religious views, it is necessary to regulate ethical-hariatic relations in the workplace as well as in Egypt. Not to mention the fact that the immoral actions of some employees, especially sexual harassment, destroy the atmosphere among employees. In addition, the inability to provide employees with a certain time and conditions for prayer at the workplace can also lead to the termination of their labor relations.

Thirdly, it is also advisable to revise the grounds for terminating the employment contract and consider the promising proposals that we made at the above paragraph. Our legislation does not contain grounds for terminating the employment contract if the employer is an individual. In addition, the grounds for terminating the employment contract are scattered, so their concentration and grouping, as in Germany, may have a good effect. The grounds for terminating the employment contract in cases independent of the will of the parties also have a large gap. It does not include the issues of termination of labor relations in connection with the death of the employer, restriction of legal

capacity or recognition of the employee as legally incompetent, recognition of the employee as missing and recognizing him as dead. Also, today the question remains open today about whether the termination of work and termination of the employment contract caused by the widespread pandemia of the coronavirus in our country will be regarded as the circumstance independent of the will of the parties. We also said in the above paragraphs that it is advisable to apply the practice of suspension, rather than terminating the employment contract, when the employee is called up for military service or fulfilling civil debt, which avoids many problems. Strengthening this rule, we would also adapt our legislation to international standards.

Fourth, the form and procedure for registration of the agreement on the termination of the employment contract are also not determined by labor legislation on what to do if the employer refuses the application for the dismissal of the employee at his own request, the issues of prohibiting the termination of the contract at the initiative of the employer are also a number of problems awaiting their decision. The application of the preliminary notification period also cannot fully protect the interests of employees. It would be nice if we learned the experience of Germany and Egypt in this matter.

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